

ELECTRICALLY CONDUCTIVE COMPOSITE : INFLUENCE OF POLYPYRROLE PARTICLES ON DYNAMIC MECHANICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF AN EPOXY MATRIX

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SUMMARY: Having in mind to produce electrically conductive carbon/epoxy composites, we have filled an insulating epoxy matrix with an electronic polymer, polypyrrole (PPy). In a previous work the characterization of epoxy/PPy particulate composites showed that the percolation threshold can be reached for PPy particles volume fraction of about 8.1%. We are now focusing our work on the dynamic mechanical behavior of particulate composites with PPy particles volume fraction laying between 0 and 14.1%. This study shows that the behavior of these composites exhibits a singularity when PPy particle volume fraction reaches 6.8%. A first analysis of this singularity has been carried out.

KEYWORDS: electrically conductive composites - percolation threshold - dynamic mechanical properties - polypyrrole - particulate filled composites

INTRODUCTION - BACKGROUND

This work is a part of our on-going research to develop an electrically conductive carbon/epoxy composite. In collaboration with Aérospatiale we have developed an electrically conductive epoxy matrix which will be used in high performance carbon/epoxy composite laminates. Polypyrrole is an intrinsically conductive polymer which exhibits a conductivity of about 6 S.cm^{-1} and a low specific mass (1200 kg.m^{-3}), but which is too brittle to carry any mechanical load by itself. By adding only 8.1% vol. particles of polypyrrole (PPy) in an epoxy matrix, we managed to increase the matrix conductivity from $10^{-12} \text{ S.cm}^{-1}$ up to $2.10^{-5} \text{ S.cm}^{-1}$. We have already shown that this conductivity value not only met the requirements of our industrial partner, but also that the conductivity was independent of the direction along which it has been measured [1]. The changes in conductivity of various epoxy/PPy blends with PPy particles volume fractions ($V_{\text{PPy}}\%$) laying between 0 and 14.1% have been examined. This study has clearly shown the presence of a percolation threshold in conductivity around $V_{\text{PPy}} =$

7.5% (Fig. 1). Furthermore, the microstructure of each blend has been carefully assessed [2]. We are now carrying out investigations on the influence of the PPy particles on the dynamic mechanical characteristics of the epoxy matrix.

Fig. 1: Electrical conductivity as a function of PPy content for PPy/epoxy particulate composites.

SAMPLES MANUFACTURING and ELECTRICAL CHARACTERIZATION

Polypyrrole synthesis

Intrinsically conductive polymer, polypyrrole (Fig. 2a) was synthesized in colloidal form via dispersion polymerization [3]. The polypyrrole (PPy) synthesis conditions are the following: 3.53 ml pyrrole monomer (Aldrich 98%) are added to a 500 ml aqueous solution of an aromatic acid (P-toluenesulfonic acid monohydrate 98% Jansen Chimica), with an oxidizing agent ammonium persulfate ((NH₄)₂S₂O₈ Janssens Chimica) and a steric stabilizer (polyvinylalcohol 96% hydrolyzed PVA96 Janssens Chimica). The oxidizing agent causes the formation of positive charges in the polymer chain and their displacement will result in the conduction phenomena. Doping anions (here paratoluenesulfonate TS⁻) which achieve the electrical neutrality of the polymer are present along the carbon backbone [4]. They result from the decomposition of the oxidizing agent. The size of PPy particles powder obtained at the end of the synthesis procedure has been determined using a LASER granulometer. The PPy particles average size is 0.5 μm.

Epoxy Resin and Preparation of the blends

For this study a bicomponent epoxy system commercialized by Hexcel Composites was used as a polymeric matrix. The commercial reference of this resin is RTM120. It consists of two prepolymer LY564 : DGEBA and DGEBD (Fig. 2b) and a curing agent HY2954 cycloaliphatic amine (Fig. 2c).

In order to prevent any curing reaction between epoxy prepolymers and curing agent, the PPy particles are added to the LY564 prepolymers only. This mixture is stirred using a Turrax (rotor-stator mixer 10 000 rpm) for 2 min. Then, after cooling the HY2954 hardener is

incorporated in this first mixture and manually stirred. Finally the whole mixture is vacuum-degassed (-20.10^2 Pa). The PPy particles volume fraction ($V_{PPy}\%$) incorporated in the epoxy matrix are laying between 0 and 14.1%. The V_{PPy} added to the epoxy matrix are the following: 0, 1.87, 6.8, 8.1, 10.4, 11.8 and 14.1%. In each case the final mixture epoxy + $V_{PPy}\%$ of polypyrrole particles is poured into a vertical mold and then cured according to the cure cycle recommended by the resin manufacturer. The 3 thermocouples embedded in the resin during cure enable to ensure firstly that there are no temperature gradients and secondly that, up to 14.1% PPy particles in the epoxy resin the temperature recorded is not at all modified.

Fig. 2: Components of particulate composites epoxy/polypyrrole.

Electrical conductivity of particulate composites

10 x 10 mm samples are cut-out from molded plates and covered with an Ag paint on which the electrodes are connected. The electrical conductivity of these particulate composite samples is then measured according to the four points probe method in two directions: along ($//$) and across (\perp) the samples. The results obtained clearly exhibit a percolation threshold (Fig. 1) located at $V_{PPy} = 7.5\%$. Around the percolation threshold the $//$ and \perp conductivities jump by five orders of magnitude and keep this value for higher PPy contents. As it can be seen in Fig. 1 the $//$ and \perp conductivities curves are identical. This proves that a homogeneous distribution of PPy particles in the epoxy matrix can be assumed whatever the particles volume fraction.

DYNAMIC MECHANICAL CHARACTERIZATION

Experimental conditions

Rectangular samples were cut-out from molded plates and submitted to 'step-iso' tests in a Polymer-Lab MKII DMTA in tensile mode. Six different frequencies (f) were used : 0.1, 1, 2, 5, 10 and 20 Hz, while the temperature was increased in 5°C steps from 40 up to 220°C

with heating ramps at 0.5°C/min between each isothermal step. Static tensile force was about 5 N and dynamic force about ± 2.5 N. The tensile strain ϵ_0 applied to the samples was about 0.045%. The DMTA tests carried out on samples with V_{PPy} laying between 0 and 14.1% enable the storage modulus E' of the particulate composites to be studied together with $\tan(\delta)$ the mechanical loss factor.

Stiffness comparison : glassy modulus

The experimental curves E' and $\tan(\delta)$ versus temperature for the frequency of 0.1 Hz and for particles volume fraction ($V_{PPy}\%$) laying between 0 and 14.1% are shown in Fig. 3. As it can be seen in Fig. 3 on storage moduli E' curves, the glassy modulus (at 40°C) of particulate composites (denoted by E'_g) does not seem to be affected by the presence of PPy particles. Indeed, whatever $V_{PPy}\%$, E'_g undergoes a $\pm 6\%$ variation around an average value of about 2140 MPa. This means that the PPy particles do not seem to have mechanical reinforcement effect. This should not be considered as a problem here, given that the main purpose for manufacturing epoxy/PPy obtaining a conductive epoxy matrix which will be used for producing carbon fibres/epoxy (epoxy/PPy) composite laminates. Consequently, since E'_g seems to be independent of $V_{PPy}\%$, our very first view could be that it is likely there might be no mechanical coupling between epoxy and PPy particles.

We have seen that when V_{PPy} reaches 6.8% electrical percolation occurs (Fig. 1). All manufactured samples have been submitted to an optical microscopy inspection which revealed that PPy particles effectively form an infinite cluster ensuring thus the conduction and that their distribution throughout the epoxy matrix was uniform [2]. However even after an energetic intensive mixing it remains some small aggregates, but none matrix areas are completely surrounded by PPy particles.

Stiffness comparison : rubbery modulus

If we now consider the rubbery modulus E'_r at temperatures higher than the glass transition temperature of the epoxy matrix ($T \approx 180^\circ\text{C}$), it can be seen on Fig. 3 that E'_r value is highly dependent on $V_{PPy}\%$. E'_r increases with increasing PPy particles volume fraction excepted for $V_{PPy}\%$ value close to the electrical percolation threshold (please refer to Fig. 1): $V_{PPy} = 8.1\%$. The values of E'_r at 0.1 Hz are reported in Table 1.

Table 1. Epoxy/PPy particulate composites at 0.1 Hz: glassy & rubbery moduli and characteristics of main mechanical relaxation (α damping peak).

$V_{PPy}\%$	E'_g (MPa)	E'_r (MPa)	T_α ($^\circ\text{C}$)	h_α	l_α ($^\circ\text{C}$)	E_α (kJ/mol)
0	2020	28	134.1	0.77	15.7	495
1.87	2050	46	142.4	0.68	15.8	635
6.8	2290	52	149.0	0.59	17.1	646
7.2	2015	48	131.7	0.51	15.3	477
8.1	1995	41	128.8	0.48	15.1	424
10.4	2120	44	138.8	0.51	21.1	537
11.8	2100	63	145.1	0.52	19.3	539
14.1	2240	66	147.6	0.53	17.9	543

Fig. 3: DMTA, tensile storage modulus E' and $\text{Tan}(\delta)$ at 0.1 Hz versus temperature for various $V_{\text{PPy}}\%$.

For analysis purpose we have manufactured a new sample with a PPy particles volume fraction of 7.2% in order to have a sample with a $V_{\text{PPy}}\%$ very close to the theoretical electrical percolation threshold ($V_{\text{PPy}} = 7.5\%$, see Fig. 1). This sample was submitted to DMTA scans according to the procedure previously used. The results obtained in terms of moduli E' (glassy and rubbery) and $\text{Tan}(\delta)$ are reported in Table 1. They clearly confirm that the rubbery modulus E'_r is decreasing for $V_{\text{PPy}}\%$ values close to the percolation threshold, since the results

obtained with $V_{PPy} = 7.2\%$ sample are very close to those obtained with $V_{PPy} = 8.1\%$ sample (see Table 1). The changes in E'_r at 0.1 Hz as a function of $V_{PPy}\%$ are shown in Fig. 4 where we have also reported the moduli predicted by Tsai-Cohen upper and lower limits [5].

Several authors have also observed that the rubbery modulus seems more sensitive to changes in particles volume fraction than the glassy modulus [6][7]. This has been explained by the existence of residual curing stresses between matrix and particles [6][8]. On the one hand, at room temperature the increase in modulus that the particles may induce is lost because of these residual curing stresses. On the other hand, at temperatures higher than the epoxy matrix T_g , the residual curing stresses are relaxed and then the reinforcement effect of particles appears. It is important to mention that in some cases the residual curing stresses generated during cooling down of samples reach a level so high that they cause cracks formation around particles. These cracks will give the polymeric matrix molecules increased volume for motion and will tend to reduce T_α [8].

Fig. 4: Rubbery modulus E'_r at 0.1 Hz as a function of $V_{PPy}\%$. Tsai - Cohen limits

Semi quantitative comparison of damping properties : α peak temperature T_α

$\tan(\delta)$ curves at 0.1 Hz are plotted in Fig. 3 versus temperature for various $V_{PPy}\%$ values. These curves give information about the main mechanical relaxation process associated to the glass transition. When comparing Fig. 3 $\tan(\delta)$ curves it becomes obvious that the PPy particles induce modifications of the main mechanical relaxation, conventionally denoted by (α) or α peak. These changes in the shape and location of the main mechanical relaxation (α peak) are generally characterized by the following parameters : T_α ($^\circ\text{C}$), the temperature at the maximum of $\tan(\delta)$ peak, h_α the amplitude of $\tan(\delta)$ peak and l_α the width of $\tan(\delta)$ peak at half height. h_α is characteristic of the amplitude of molecular movements of the transition, whereas l_α is representative of the homogeneity of the macromolecular crosslinked network

[9].

T_α ($^\circ\text{C}$), h_α and l_α ($^\circ\text{C}$) values determined on $\text{Tan}(\delta)$ curves at 0.1 Hz are given in Table 1. These values have been used to build Fig. 5 where T_α and h_α at 0.1 Hz are plotted versus $V_{\text{PPy}}\%$. Furthermore we have plotted in Fig. 5 the h_α prediction given by the Nielsen [13] theoretical relation (eqn. 1).

$$h_a^c = h_a^m \cdot (1 - V_{\text{PPy}}) \quad (1)$$

With : h_a^c , α peak height of composite
and h_a^m , α peak height of unfilled matrix

Several authors have observed on polymer matrix/metal or ceramic particulate composites that T_α increases with increasing values of $V_{\text{PPy}}\%$ [10][11][12], whereas h_α decreases. The increase in T_α with particle volume fraction is classically attributed to the residual curing stresses between particles and matrix (as we have seen for rubbery modulus) [7][8] and/or a reduction in the mobility of macromolecular chains segments due to the absorption of some epoxy chains segments at particles surface [11][14].

As it can be seen in Fig. 5, the situation with epoxy/PPy particulate composites seems to be more complex, we should keep in mind that the polypyrrole is a polymer. From $V_{\text{PPy}} = 0\%$ the α peak temperature T_α ($^\circ\text{C}$) increases when increasing $V_{\text{PPy}}\%$ up to 6.8% just before the beginning of the electric percolation (see also Fig. 1). For $V_{\text{PPy}}\%$ values at which the electrical percolation occurs (between 6.8 and 8.1%), T_α undergoes a decrease. Finally, when $V_{\text{PPy}}\%$ passes 8.1% the upward trend in T_α reappears, but T_α value for $V_{\text{PPy}} = 14.1\%$ remains below the maximum recorded just before the beginning of the electrical percolation.

Fig. 5: Changes in α peak temperature T_α and height h_α depending on $V_{\text{PPy}}\%$ (at 0.1 Hz) and Nielsen prediction [13].

Semi quantitative comparison of damping properties : α peak amplitude h_α

Concerning the amplitude of the α peak, h_α , the information given by Table 1 and Fig. 5 is more scattered. It is quite impossible to bring out any whole trend of the changes in h_α . For $V_{\text{PPy}}\%$ values laying between 0 and 6.8%, h_α decreases with the increase in $V_{\text{PPy}}\%$. This seems

to be in good accordance with the corresponding changes in T_α and in E'_r . (when $0 \leq V_{PPy} \leq 6.8\%$). Similar phenomenon are usually reported in studies of particulate composites [12][15] [16]. For a such behavior, as we have already said, it is hypothesized that the particles induce a reduction in the mobility of macromolecular chains in their vicinity corresponding to a stiffening of the epoxy/particles interface due to strong bonds between matrix and particles. When $6.8\% < V_{PPy} \leq 8.1\%$, h_α curve exhibits a sharp trough and for $V_{PPy}\%$ values higher than 8.1% h_α seems to rise slowly.

As shown in Table 1, the α peak width at half height, l_α ($^\circ\text{C}$) undergoes small changes depending on the particles volume fraction. The epoxy macromolecular crosslinked network seems to remain rather homogeneous whatever $V_{PPy}\%$, excepted for 10.4% and 11.8% where l_α values are higher than all the other ones. In these two cases, it can be though that the presence of the particles induce homogeneity modifications.

Activation energy E_α

The relaxation process associated to glass transition can be characterized by an apparent activation energy determined from the shift factor a_T in the WLF equation. Nevertheless, in this study, the apparent activation energy (for glass transition) E_α ($\text{kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$) has been obtained by plotting $\ln(f)$ versus $1/T_\alpha$ (K^{-1}) Eqn 2. The E_α values thus determined are reported in Table 1.

$$\ln(a_T) = \ln\left(\frac{f}{f_0}\right) = \frac{E_\alpha}{R} \cdot \left[\frac{1}{T_\alpha} - \frac{1}{T_{ref}} \right] \quad (2)$$

with : f_0 , reference frequency (Hz)

R , universal gas constant

T_{ref} , reference temperature (K^{-1})

T_α , α peak temperature (maximum of $\text{Tan}(\delta)$ curves) [18]

The maximum difference in apparent activation energy is of about 35%. The changes in E_α follow those that we have already seen for T_α depending on $V_{PPy}\%$. When $0 \leq V_{PPy} \leq 6.8\%$, E_α increases with increasing $V_{PPy}\%$. When $6.8\% < V_{PPy} \leq 8.1\%$, E_α decreases and when $V_{PPy}\%$ passes 8.1% , E_α increases again.

DISCUSSION

For polypyrrole particles volume fraction up to 6.8% , the obtained results show that the composite epoxy/PPy behaves like most other particulate composites : $E'_r \uparrow$, $T_\alpha \uparrow$, $h_\alpha \downarrow$ and $E_\alpha \uparrow$ with increasing $V_{PPy}\%$ values and the comments that could be associated to these changes are still those we have already mentioned. The reduction in the macromolecular mobility can attributed to epoxy chain segments absorption on particles surface and/or residual curing stresses. Nevertheless, we should add that besides chain segments absorption on particles surface and residual curing stresses, some authors also put forward an increase in matrix degree of cure in particles vicinity [12] or interactions between particles [13]. So in that range of $V_{PPy}\%$, in spite of polypyrrole being a polymer, the epoxy/polypyrrole particles composites exhibit a behavior similar to the behavior of polymer matrix and ceramic (or metallic) particulates composites. Furthermore, the increase in E_α value with $V_{PPy}\%$ shows that there are interactions between epoxy and PPy particles and that their intensity grows with increasing $V_{PPy}\%$.

When $6.8\% < V_{PPy} \leq 8.1\%$, we have seen that $E'_r \nearrow$, $T_\alpha \searrow$, $h_\alpha \searrow$ and $E_\alpha \searrow$. From these results it can be assumed that there seems to be now less interactions between epoxy chains segments and particles than there used to be when $V_{PPy} < 6.8\%$. The strong decrease in the apparent activation energy with increasing $V_{PPy}\%$ values between 6.8 and 8.1% backs up this assertion. So, this shows that the composites behave as if the intensity or the quantity of matrix / particles interactions had decreased. However, we should keep in mind that from $V_{PPy} = 6.8\%$ the epoxy matrix becomes electrically conductive. This means (and it has been confirmed by the optical micrographs [2]) that PPy particles now form an infinite cluster. Consequently, since there are no particular reason for which matrix/particles interactions might change, it is likely that this is the consequence of particle/particle interaction. But if this is assumed, then how can it be explained that in polymer/ceramic (or metallic) particulate composites, particles/particles interactions account for increases (and not decreases) in T_α ? The main difference is that here the particles are a polymer instead of a ceramic or a metal and that the mechanical properties of this polymer (polypyrrole) are certainly lower than those of the epoxy matrix. Then it could be hypothesized that there is a kind of phase change in the composite. However, we do think that the polypyrrole particles volume fractions remain too low for a phase inversion to occur.

Lets now examine what is going on when $8.1 < V_{PPy}\%$. In that $V_{PPy}\%$ range, $E'_r \nearrow$, $T_\alpha \nearrow$, $h_\alpha \nearrow$ and $E_\alpha \nearrow$. The increase in T_α , h_α and E_α counteracts the assumptions we have just made. Nonetheless, even if T_α , h_α and E_α undergo an increase, their values (reported in Table 1) remain lower than those recorded before the onset of the electrical percolation or before $V_{PPy} > 6.8\%$. However, this shows that when V_{PPy} passes 6.8%, the behavior of the particulate composite at glass transition temperature is in a way modified.

It is clear that several further experiments are necessary to bear out or belie these results and unravel the singularity introduced by polypyrrole particles that we are not in a position to explain today. Nevertheless, we think important to mention that the range of particles volume fractions analysed here (from 0 up to 14.1%) remains very limited when compared to those usually studied in particulate composites (0% \rightarrow ~40%).

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